

西南交通大学
Southwest Jiaotong University

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Reaction assisted flash sintering of Al_2O_3 –YAG eutectic component ceramic

Jinling Liu¹, Xiang Xu², Dianguang Liu², Linan An³

¹School of Mechanics and Engineering, Southwest Jiaotong University, Chengdu, Sichuan 610031, China

²School of Materials Science and Engineering, Southwest Jiaotong University, Chengdu, Sichuan 610031, China

³Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Central Florida, Orlando, FL 32816, USA

Content

- Flash sintering
 - Phenomenon of flash sintering
 - Electric field enhanced diffusion
- Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders
 - Phase transition
 - Microstructure
 - Mechanical properties
 - Eutectic phase
- Summary

■ Phenomenon of flash sintering

- Flash sintering was firstly reported by Rish Raj's group in 2010.

- Flash sintering has been found to be successful in ionic conductors, semiconductors, electronic conductors, and insulators.

- ✓ **YSZ**
- ✓ Al_2O_3
- ✓ Y_2O_3
- ✓ ZnO
- ✓ SnO_2
- ✓ TiO_2
- ✓ Co_2MnO_4
- ✓ SrTiO_3
- ✓ KNbO_3
- ✓ $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YSZ}$
- ✓ $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{TiO}_2$
- ✓ ...

■ Phenomenon of flash sintering

➤ Abnormal conductivity

Current pass through the specimen during flash sintering.

The power spike indicates a highly non-linear increase in the conductivity of the specimen.

It argued that the sudden increase in electrical conductivity arising from Joule heating.

■ Phenomenon of flash sintering

➤ Photoemission

3YSZ

J. Lebrun, et al., J. Am. Ceram. Soc., 97 [8] 2427–2430 (2014).

K. Terauds, et al., J. Europ. Ceram. Soc., 35, 3195–3199(2015) .

■ Phenomenon of flash sintering

➤ Ultra-fast densification at low temperature

High density have been achieved in a few seconds.

The densification rate is much higher than other technology.

■ Electric field enhanced diffusion

➤ Improved sinterability

ZrO₂/SiC_w Composites

D. Liu et al. J.Eur. Ceram. Soc. 36, 2051-2055(2016).

Ternary Eutectic

D. Liu et al. Scripta Materialia 114, 108-111(2016).

■ Electric field enhanced diffusion

➤ Chemical reaction & phase transition

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ binary system

$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$

900 °C

YAM

1100 °C

YAP

1400 °C

YAG

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-YAG}$ was flash sintered with high E & T

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ Mixed phase after soaking at different temperature

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ Solid state reaction assisted flash sintering

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ Mixed phase after soaking at different time

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ Flash sintering was impeded due to less reactions

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ Fast phase transition with flash sintering

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ Microstructure

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ Hardness & fracture toughness

Sample	FS	DS
Hv (GPa)@9.8N	13±0.5	18.7
K_{IC} (MPa•m ^{1/2})	4.8±0.5	3.6

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ Soaking at low temperature

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

- Flash sintering at low temperature with reactions

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

➤ The temperature evolution during flash sintering

Flash sintering $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ powders

Anode

Center

Cathode

10 S

30 S

50 S

Summary

- The mixed Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 powders can be flash sintered at 800 °C under the applied electrical field of 900 V/cm.
- The solid-state reactions between Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 facilitate the flash sintering process.
- The sintered Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 ceramic composites exhibit relatively high hardness and high fracture toughness.
- It demonstrate the feasibility of employing the flash sintering technique to fabricate oxide eutectic ceramic.

Acknowledgements

1. Grant No. 51672227, Research on the mechanism of flash sintering Al₂O₃/YAG/ZrO₂ eutectic ceramics, 2017.1-2020.12.
2. Grant No. 51732009, Processing and mechanism of flash sintering, 2018.01-2022.12.
3. Grant No. 51802271, Superplastic deformation mechanism of 3YSZ at low temperature and high strain rate, 2019.01-2021.12.

西南交通大学
Southwest Jiaotong University

ICCM22
MELBOURNE
AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

